

SOME PECULIARITIES OF FORMATION OF AMERICAN VARIANT OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The article dwells on some functioning peculiarities of prepositions in two languages, the level of discrepancy of grammar prepositional constructions in British and American variants of the English language.

Key words: dialect, migration, functioning of the prepositions, ‘americanisms’

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At the beginning of the 17th century colonists from England began bringing their language to America. The first settlement of the Englishmen in North America was founded in 1607 – it was Jamestown on the territory of the current state of Virginia. The city of Plymouth was founded in 1620 by the puritans come by ‘Mayflower’. The citizens of these two settlements had different language traditions. The colonists of Jamestown mostly came from such western parts of England as counties Somerset and Gloucestershire with the peculiar pronunciation of these regions. The colonists of Plymouth were coming from eastern counties of England (Lincolnshire, Essex, Kent) and London, where dialects were quite different.

Massive migration into a new country – the United States of America – still went on in the XIX-XX centuries. However, the vast variety of languages and cultures, the leading language was still English.

Moreover, poly-cultural character of the United States can be seen in anthroponomy, in proper nouns that kept their national features: Spanish – Rodolfo, Dolores; Italian – Antonio, Niccolo, Paolo; German – Rupert, Rudolf, etc. however, the English language of the north American colonies was enriched by borrowings. The settlers borrowed from Indian language to describe unknown objects: hickory, persimmon, raccoon, woodchuck; from French: chowder, prairie, scow, sleigh, etc.

The reason for appearance of new words took place due to the fact that many new realias appeared in the life of former Europeans as they had no words to call the new objects in their own language. Besides lexicon, there also was the difference in pronunciation, grammar construction and especially in intonation.

Despite the fact that British and American English are the variants of the same language, there is a range of differences between them.

In British English preposition has the special use with the words ‘next’ and ‘last’: My friend Jackie lives next door but one.

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In American and colloquial British English, we can omit 'on' with the days of week: See you (on) Tuesday.

You can start work (on) Friday morning.

With the names of streets we use 'in' in British and 'on' in American:

She lives in Hazel Avenue.

She lives on Hazel Avenue.

In Hyde Park, at Central Park.

In the expressions 'at the edge' and 'at the side' we can notice 'on', especially in American English:

On the edge of a cliff.

We do not need 'at' in American English expression 'at home':

Br.: Is anybody at home?

I flayed at home all day yesterday.

Am.: Is anybody home?

Prepositions 'round' and 'around' determine a circle movement, but Americans use only 'around'.

Br.E.: (A)round the corner, to sit round a table, to rock (a)round the clock, to turn (a)round, to sleep (a)round the clock.

Am.E.: Around the corner, to sit around the table, to rock around the clock, to turn around, to sleep around the clock.

Will you hand round the papers? Can I look around?

Now we will demonstrate some differences in preposition use or their omission in British and American English:

To meet smb. / to meet with smb.

To visit smb. / to visit with smb.

To speak to smb. / to speak with smb.

To talk to smb. / to talk with smb.

To write to smb. / to write smb.

To protest against smth. / to protest smth.

To fill in a form / to fill a form.

To check smth. / to check smth out.

To do smth. again / to do smth. over.

Monday to Friday / Monday through Friday.

At the weekends / on the weekends.

Different from / to / different from / than.

Apart from / aside from.

Stay at home / stay home.

On behalf of / in behalf of.

In this article we tried to find out some peculiarities of preposition functioning in two variants of the English language and the level of dissimilarity of grammar prepositional constructions.

Some European languages influenced the grammar of the American English as well. That is why in comparison with the British English, the American English is more flexible, revealed for the changes and easy for reception due to which it spread world-wide.

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